

**Youth
Goals**

EUYPD10

WE NEED YOUTH

EUYPD10 Results of the Survey
Consultations: We Need Youth

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EUYD10 Standardised Survey Results

During the consultation phase of the 10th Cycle of the EU Youth Dialogue (EUYD10), some of the National Working Groups (NWGs) decided to use a standardised survey as one of the consultation methods. An international dataset was constructed by merging the datasets from the NWGs¹, and this dataset was used to provide results which are presented in this report.

Table 1: Targets of the European Youth Goal no. 3 and references to questions of the EUYD10 survey.

Targets of the Youth Goal no. 3: Inclusive Societies	Questions covering the targets
1. Provide legal protection and enforce international legal instruments to fight against all kinds of discrimination and hate speech, recognising that young people are subjected to multiple forms of discrimination.	Q9, Q10, Q11
2. Strengthen outreach of information to marginalised young people, to ensure they are aware of spaces, opportunities and experiences available to them.	Q13
3. Ensure that all marginalised young people have equal access to formal and non-formal learning environments, addressing all the dimensions of inclusion.	Q14, Q17
4. Strengthen the capacities of educators to work with marginalised young people.	Q15, Q16
5. Provide more spaces, opportunities, resources and programmes to foster dialogue and social cohesion, and combat discrimination and segregation.	Q12
6. Strengthen social support by implementing the right to a living wage, fair work conditions, universal access to quality health care, and ensure specific measures for marginalised young people.	Q18, Q19
7. Ensure that marginalised young people are participating in all decision-making processes and are key players, particularly in processes concerning their own rights, wellbeing and interests.	Q20

In total, 16 questions were asked to monitor the backgrounds of respondents, and further 12 questions were used to inquire about various aspects of the European Youth Goal no. 3: Inclusive Societies, as shown in the following tables. The Table 1 shows the relevant targets of the European Youth Goal no. 3,

¹ For details of dataset construction as well as of background of survey respondents, please refer to the Annex.

and also pinpoints concrete survey questions which covered the given target. The subsequent Table 2 shows the concrete questions which were used in the EUYD10 standardised survey. An index² was constructed based on the questions listed in this table that summarises the perceived implementation of the European Youth Goal no. 3 by young people across the EU: **the youth perception index of social inclusion**. This report summarises results of this index across various subgroups of young people, answering the question **“To what extent do young people consider current society inclusive?”**.

Table 2: EUYD10 survey questions related to the European Youth Goal no. 3.

How much do you agree with the following statements?				
Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree	Can't judge / Don't know
Q9 Hate speech is present in online environments that I use.				
Q10 Hate speech is present where I live, such as at playgrounds, libraries, restaurants, and so on.				
Q11 Discrimination is present where I live.				
Q12 I have the opportunity to take part in dialogue with people who are from different backgrounds to me.				
Q13 I have good access to information about opportunities for young people.				
Q14 If I wanted to, I could join a youth club or a youth project.				
Q15 Teachers understand my needs.				
Q16 Youth workers and youth leaders understand my needs.				
Q17 School was/is a place where I felt/feel well included.				
Q18 If I was looking for work, I could find a good quality job.				
Q19 If I needed it, I could access good quality healthcare.				
Q20 I can make my voice heard in my community.				

The youth perception index of social inclusion (furthermore “the Index”) is a scale which ranges from low perceptions represented by a 0, to high perceptions represented by a 10. The higher the average, the more positively young people perceived the state of inclusion in European societies. As shown in Figure 1, for the whole sample of young people who filled in the EUYD10 survey, the average figure is 5.28. This clearly shows that young people see inclusive societies as far from being reality, although

² The youth perception index of social inclusion is a summative index calculated as a sum of all questions in Table 2. The resulting index was subsequently re-sized to fit the desired scale of zero to ten.

they appreciate that the European communities work at a certain level of inclusiveness. Further analyses were conducted to compare views of young people from different walks of life.

Figure 1: Youth perception index of social inclusion. 0 means low level of inclusion and 10 means high level of inclusion in society.

Figure 2: Youth perception index of social inclusion in young people with and without hate speech and discrimination experience.

Firstly, as shown in Figure 2, young people with different experience of hate speech and/or discrimination were compared³. It is obvious that those without any such negative experience rate the European societies as more inclusive (score of 5.29) than those who have first-hand hate speech and/or discrimination experience (scores of 5.19 and 5.08). Interestingly, it is the young people with discrimination experience that feel more critical on the state of inclusion in the European society (see Figure 3, score 5.05), while those young people who were victims of hate speech tend to think more positively about the inclusion levels in Europe. It is possible that while hate speech can have a positive outcome (e.g., someone standing up against the aggressor), the discrimination is often a very different situation with much less likelihood of anyone intervening, and hence the impacts of these two experiences can be very different.

Figure 3: Youth perception index of social inclusion in young people with and without hate speech and discrimination experience, separate group analysis.

Interestingly, young people who are not in employment, education, or training (NEET) perceive social inclusion in Europe in a much more positive light than their counterparts who are active either in the labour market or in education (see Figure 4). Figure 5 shows that the most positive views of inclusion can be found in those young people who do not work (score of 5.58) and those who are in full time education (score of 5.46). This result is understandable, because 82% of those in full time education also do not work, in other words, these two groups overlap greatly. A similar overlap can be seen in

³ This group was identified based on the following questions:

- I have been a victim of hate speech. (Somebody spoke to me very unkindly because of my ethnic, religious, or other background.) YES/NO
- I have been a victim of discrimination. (Somebody treated me differently than others because of my ethnic, religious, or other background.) YES/NO

Depending on the answers the respondents gave, they fell into one of the following categories: those who self-identified as victims of both hate speech and discrimination; those who self-identified as victims of either of the two; those who did not self-identify as victims of either.

the two groups that score the lowest: the part-time employed (score of 4.74) and those not in education (score of 5.16). Among those who are employed part-time, almost 70% are not in education.

Figure 4: Youth perception index of social inclusion in majority and NEET young people.

In summary, the two groups that view the inclusion very differently are those that are in full time education and do not work (positive views of inclusion), and those who are in part-time employment and not in education (negative views of inclusion).

Figure 5: Youth perception index of social inclusion across young people with different educational and labour market status.

Figure 6: Youth perception index of social inclusion in young people with fewer opportunities and majority youth.

Figure 6 shows that young people with fewer opportunities⁴ see inclusion more positively than their counterparts, the majority youth. This seemingly strange result can be explained by further exploring various aspects that were taken into account when creating the category of young people with fewer opportunities, namely: ethnic minority background, religious minority background, sexual minority background (i.e., lesbian, gay, bisexual or any sexuality other than heterosexual), disability, long term health conditions, and young people living in a rural or remote area.

Figure 7 shows standalone analyses for young people from different walks of life, all of whom were summarised by the category of young people with fewer opportunity. It is apparent that in most of these sub-groups, inclusion is indeed more critically viewed by young people from minority backgrounds, most notably those from ethnic minorities, and disabled youth. Nevertheless, that is not the case for young people from religious minority backgrounds (see Figure 8). This exception can have many explanations: there are many religions and even if a given religion is not the one held by majority of people in a given country, it does not need to constitute a disadvantage; to some extent, religion is a private matter that does not need to constitute a disadvantage simply by not being present in public life of a given young person; and many other. All in all, it is important to notice that perceptions of inclusion are not homogenous across various groups which are often labelled as disadvantaged, or as young people with fewer opportunities. This can be due to different nature of the disadvantage, and hence due to a different level of inclusion (i.e., in some cases inclusion measures can be well targeted and well implemented), but it can also be due to a different understanding of inclusion among young

⁴ This category was created as a summary index of the questions in which respondents self-identified as members of the following groups:

- ethnic minority background,
- religious minority background,
- sexual minority background (i.e., lesbian, gay, bisexual or any sexuality other than heterosexual),
- disability,
- long term health conditions, and
- young people living in a rural or remote area.

In case a respondent answered “yes” to at least one of the questions above, they would fall into the category of young people with fewer opportunities.

people from different walks of life. A similar situation can be seen in case of young people who marked themselves as not belonging to male or female genders (see Figure 9). While male and female young people score very similarly to each other and to the general average score, youth from other genders sees inclusion in a much more positive light. This can, again, have similar explanations to those provided above.

Figure 7: Youth perception index of social inclusion in young people from various backgrounds, part 1.

Figure 8: Youth perception index of social inclusion in young people from various backgrounds, part II.

Figure 9: Youth perception index of social inclusion across genders.

Figure 10: Youth perception index of social inclusion in young people with ethnic minority background across genders.

* There are too few respondents in the "Other gender" category and hence no results are reported.

Two intersectional analyses were also conducted, and the results can be seen in Figure 10 and Figure 11. Intersectionality is a concept which describes an accumulation of disadvantages by a single person. In the two examples, these young people belong to different genders (male and female) and at the same time also belong to an ethnic minority (Figure 10) or are disabled (Figure 11). Results show that effects of multiple disadvantages can be clearly seen in these two examples: females who also belong to an ethnic minority as well as females who also belong to a group of disabled youth both score much lower in the youth perception index of social inclusion than their male counterparts and also than their counterparts from other backgrounds.

This result suggests that at least in some cases, intersectionality (i.e., cumulative disadvantage) negatively affects how young people perceive inclusiveness of the society. In other words, while results in previous figures focused on young people from different backgrounds, these results show that young people with combined backgrounds, such as females from ethnic minority groups, are perceiving inclusiveness at even lower levels.

This report does not include all potential intersectional analyses for two reasons. Firstly, there are too many potential combinations to analyse, providing too many details and going against the purpose of this report: to provide clear and comprehensive information on how young people perceive inclusiveness of current societies. Secondly, as shown above, not all groups considered as disadvantaged show consistent results when it comes to the youth perception index of social inclusion. Therefore, more detailed measures would need to be taken in any future survey to enable results to be correctly interpreted, such as concrete religious denominations, and others.

Figure 11: Youth perception index of social inclusion in disabled young people across genders.

* There are too few respondents in the "Other gender" category and hence no results are reported.

Key Takeaways

- Standardised survey was conducted by some National Working Groups as part of the consultations with young people during the 10th Cycle of the EU Youth Dialogue.
- European Youth Goal no. 3: Inclusive Societies was explored via the survey and quantified through a *Youth perception index of social inclusion*.
- Young people do not see inclusion as very well developed, but they also do not see this domain as a failure, with an average index score of 5.28 on a scale from 0 (low perception of inclusion) to 10 (high perception of inclusion).
- Young people from various backgrounds see inclusion differently.
- Not all sub-groups of young people who are traditionally labelled as disadvantaged or as young people with fewer opportunities view inclusion less favourably than majority youth.
- This can be due to different nature of the disadvantage, and hence due to a different level of inclusion (i.e., in some cases inclusion measures can be well targeted and well implemented), but it can also be due to a different understanding of inclusion among young people from different walks of life.
- Intersectionality plays a role in young people's perceptions of social inclusion, with at least some cumulative disadvantages leading to worsening of the social inclusion perceptions.

Annex: NWG Surveys in EUYD10: Background of Respondents

Standardised EUYD10 surveys were part of the national consultations of 12 National Working Groups that submitted data for international analyses, namely:

- Austria,
- Belgium (German-speaking community),
- Croatia,
- Cyprus,
- Estonia,
- Germany,
- Italy,
- Luxembourg,
- Malta,
- Netherlands,
- Slovakia, and
- Sweden.

In total, 10748 respondents filled in the surveys. After cleaning the data (i.e., removing responses from respondents who do not belong to the target age group of 13-34, and those who filled in less than 75% of the survey questions), there were 8827 valid answers from 10 National Working Groups.

The sample was subsequently weighted in order to best represent ratios of young people in the respective countries. The only exception is the German-speaking community of Belgium, which was not weighted as no region-specific data on numbers of young people were available. As a result, a sample of 7655 responses was used for international analyses of the EUYD10 survey consultations.

Figure 12: Age distribution of survey respondents.

Figure 13: Background of survey respondents, part I.

Respondents of the standardised EUYD10 survey were on average 25 years old, with the most respondents aged 26 to 30 as shown in *Figure 12*. The survey respondents were more often women, with a small minority of those who identify in other gender categories, and they came from various backgrounds, including those of ethnic (4.8%), religious (7.7%), sexual (17.6%), or health-based (3.8% and 13.2%) minorities (see *Figure 13*). The respondents also came from rural areas (19.1%), and some of them were members of language minorities (5.6%; see *Figure 14*).

Figure 14: Background of survey respondents, part II.

Figure 15: Background of survey respondents, part III.

Most of the respondents did not work and were not in education at the time of filling in the survey (48.5%), with slightly more than half of respondents working either full time (28%) or part time (23.5%), and with a large percentage of the respondents in full time education (42.3%; see *Figure 14*). All in all, only 7% of the respondents were not in employment, education, or training (NEETs).

About one third of respondents have been victims of hate speech and about one quarter of them have been victims of discrimination (see *Figure 15*). Altogether, about two thirds of the respondents have no experience with hate speech or discrimination, about 15% have experience with either of these negative phenomena, and about 21% experienced both. Moreover, about 45% of the respondents fell into the category of young people with fewer opportunities due to them belonging to one or more of the minority categories described above. In terms of economic stability, respondents are fairly balanced on the scale between those who feel they do not have economic hardships, and those who feel they are struggling (see *Figure 17*).

More detailed analyses show that there are many more victims of hate speech and discrimination among young people with fewer opportunities than among majority youth (see *Figure 16*). Those who experienced both hate speech and discrimination account for about 9% in majority youth, but for about 33% in young people with fewer opportunities. Those who experienced one of these negative phenomena account for about 12% in majority youth, but for about 17% in young people with fewer opportunities.

Figure 16: Ratios of victims of hate speech and discrimination in majority youth and in YPFO youth.

All in all, the standardised EUYD survey managed to capture opinions of young people from various walks of life, those who can be characterised as majority in the EU society, as well as those who fall into various minority groups, and those who are better and worse off economically. The survey also largely managed to capture opinions of those young people who were not previously engaged in EUYD processes and activities, as only about 18% of the respondents already took part in any EUYD activities prior to taking part in the survey.

Figure 17: Economic stability of young people and their EUYD engagement.

